

AN RFID AUTHENTICATION PROTOCOL FOR SECURITY AND PRIVACY

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Abstract— Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) uses tags which contain electronic product code (EPC). This EPC is sent to reader without any guard. Invading this EPC, results in various RFID security threats. Security plays a vital role in various RFID applications. In order to provide security, several protocols are developed based on traditional encryption methods, such as cryptographic and hash functions. However, they do not pave way for low cost RFID tags. Based on Gen2, an authentication protocol for security and privacy is proposed for low-cost RFID tags. This protocol is based on Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) and Hamming Distance Calculation in order to achieve reader-to-tag authentication and the memory read command is used to achieve tag-to-reader authentication. It will resist against tracing and cloning attacks in the most efficient way.

Index Terms—electronic product code, hamming distance, cyclic redundancy check, authentication, memory read.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radio frequency identification (RFID) technology has started to flourish in the recent years. RFID uses radio waves for the automatic identification of the objects. However, RFID capabilities are yet to be innovated with deeper vision. An outburst has occurred in many areas of research with RFID such as supply chain management, information systems, project management, e-commerce, warehousing, etc. Various RFID applications include library management, smart home appliances, traffic systems, airport applications, healthcare, industry, military applications such as monitoring borders and control lines, etc. RFID, having unique features such as many to many communications, wireless data transmissions and computing nature, draws attention from organizations like Wal-Mart, Proctor & Gamble Co., Nokia, IBM, Infosys for investing in it.

A. RFID SYSTEMS COMPONENTS

The major components of RFID system are the following: RFID Reader, RFID Tags and Antenna. An RFID reader is a device that is used to interrogate RFID tags. The reader has an antenna that emits radio waves; the tag responds by sending back its data. RFID Tags falls under two main categories: Passive Tags and Active tags. Passive tags do not possess battery and it derives energy from RFID reader whereas Active tags get energy from its own battery. After receiving tag data, reader decodes it and sends it to backend database. Reader communicates with the database using RFID application software via RFID application peripheral interface.

B. SECURITY WEAKNESS

There are several security and privacy threats which mitigate the growth of RFID in various applications. Ironically the security weakness of RFID technologies lies in the RFID tags' basic operation of sending a unique identification code known as electronic product code (EPC). EPC is specific to the object associated with the tag. Using the unique EPC, unauthorized access of tracking the moving history, the personal preference and the belongings of a tag's holder can be done.

C. SECURITY THREATS

Studies [3], [4], [5] reveal the following security threats in RFID:

- Eaves dropping: Attacker listens to all the communications.
- Replay attack: Attacker repeats the same messages logged from eaves dropping.
- Cloning: Attacker clones the tag itself.
- Tag tracing: Attacker can easily trace the tag and communicate with it.
- Data forging: Data about the several items may be changed by the attacker.

- Invading privacy: Privacy of the customers is affected.

D. SECURITY SOLUTIONS

Problems due to those threats resulted in the development of security protocols. Lots of researchers have proposed several lightweight cryptographic protocols. Most of the proposed solutions make use of a hash function and cryptographic functions. Though they provide the security, it results in high cost RFID. Some of the protocols are the following: Hash-based protocols[5][10][11], Hash-chain based solution[15], Signature-based protocol[16], Public key-based protocol[17] and Light weight solutions[18][19]. In CRC-based protocol [3], PIN is used to protect sessions directly. But it still suffers from desynchronization attacks.

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

A. Protocol Definition

In this protocol, no cryptographic or hash function is used. Mutual authentication between appropriate readers and tags is achieved by randomizing each session. Authentication Process is based on the CRC16 (Cyclic Redundancy Check), pseudo random number generation and threshold value. A threshold value and a set of strings called key values are written into each tag using MEMWRITE command.

Block Diagram

Connection Details

Step 2: All drawn pseudonyms (16-bit strings) are passed through a majority function in bitwise.

Step 3: A majority function outputs “1” if its input contains more 1’s than 0’s; otherwise, it outputs “0”.

Step 4: The output of each bit position forms the final 16-bit ck’.

B. Protocol Implementation

Algorithm 1. Authentication process Algorithm

Step 1: The reader sends Query command to select a specific tag.

Step 2a: The tag responds with 16-bit random number, $k[a:b]$. The tag calculates the CRC residue of $k[a:b]$ and keeps the residue, ck .

Step 2b: The reader simply forwards this number to the back-end database.

Step 3: The database then generates a 16-bit number ck' , called the central key. This value is sent back to the reader and the tag as well.

Step 4: The tag compares ck' with ck . If their Hamming distance is smaller than a threshold value t , the tag believes that the reader is legal.

Algorithm 2. Central key Generating Algorithm

Step 1: Perform CRC-16 computations on each key value marked by (a, b) within the database.

- 1.Tag sends 16 bit Random number to reader.
- 2.Reader forwards the received number to server.
- 3.Backend server sends central key to reader.
- 4.Reader sends the received central key to tag.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A set of strings (key values) are stored in the database. The calculation of CRC16 for each key value is done. And the implementation of majority function is performed at the server side. Let 16 bit data received from tag be

00000000 00000011

It is used to determine the key values from Database.

Key values are the following:

- 012345
- 345612
- 234510
- 765121
- 432147
- AD2165
- 32ABF4
- 514032

CRC16 COMPUTATIONS

- key value1 : 012345
CRC16 : 5450h 0101010001010000
- key value2 : 345612
CRC16 : 80CFh 1000000011001111
- key value3 : 234510
CRC16 : AC0Bh 1010110000001011
- key value4 : 765121
CRC16 : F446h 1111010001000110
- key value5 : 432147
CRC16 : 1108h 0001000100001000
- key value6 : AD2165
CRC16 : DE77h 1101111001110111
- key value7 : 32ABF4
CRC16 : 98BBh 1001100010111011
- key value8 : 514032
CRC16 : 7BE3h 0111101111100011

Implementation of Majority Function

Central key ck is sent to the rfid reader. The reader forwards it to tag. The tag determines the Hamming distance using the received central key value. Tag responds only if the

hamming distance is less than the threshold value. Each session is randomized by changing the key values and threshold values periodically using MEMWRITE command. Privacy can be achieved by setting threshold value to zero when the tagged object is sold. Various security analyses are done to show the mutual authentication between tag and reader and also from reader to tag.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This protocol is based on Gen 2 protocol and it permits every message flow of it and it results in low cost RFID tags. The tag requires no cryptographic operations but only a Hamming distance calculator and some memory space. This protocol is a fortress against various RFID security threats. In future, this protocol can be implemented along with the concept of fingerprinting RFID tags. Further, sending the number of bits from tag to reader can also be minimized in order to boost the reading speed. This protocol also be implemented in rfid tags of various frequency ranges.

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